

Histochemical Studies Of Lipofuscin Pigment Of Aging In Mature Age In Brain Of *Rattus Rattus*

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Rupali Tripathi
Assistant Professor
Department Of Zoology
Bundelkhand University
Jhansi U.P., India

Devendra Pandey
Professor
Department Of Zoology
Bundelkhand University
Jhansi, U.P., India

Abstract In the present investigation the histochemical nature of lipofuscin pigment in brain cells of mature age of *Rattus rattus*. The lipofuscin pigment in brain cells of mature age level reacted strongly with Nile blue A method, reacted moderately to Ferric ferricyanide method and mildly affinities with carbol fuchsin method.

Keywords *Rattus Rattus*, Brain Tissue, Lipofuscin Stains Nile Blue A, Ferric Ferricyanide, Carbol Fuchsin.

Introduction Lipofuscin pigment is yellowish brown colour autofluorescent intracytoplasmic pigment .It gradually accumulates in long lived postmitotic cells such as neurons, skeletal muscles,cardiac muscles . Aging can be described as an unchanging halt of the cell attached to stereotyped phenotypic modifications.

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to analyse the histochemical studies of Lipofuscin Pigment of aging In mature age in brain of *Rattus Rattus*.

Review of Literature Hayflick suggested this method in human fibroblast serially passed in culture (Hayflick and Moorhead, 1961) deposition of lipofuscin pigment is the process of aging. The process of lipofuscin accumulation occurs continuously throughout the life of all organisms.

Methodology The material used in the study brain cells from mature age group. Tissue samples were fixed in bouin's fluid, tissues were then transformed in alcoholic series and material were kept molten paraffin and blocks were prepared and paraffin sections cut at 6µ thickness. Stains with Nile blue A, Ferric ferricyanide and carbol fuchsin for histochemical study.

Result and Discussion In the present investigation, the lipofuscin pigments in brain cells of mature age level of *Rattus rattus*, reacted strongly with Nile blue A, reacted moderately with ferric ferricyanide and mildly with carbol fuchsin method. Similarly these stains were used in [1] & [5] results revealed that in the mature age group pigment accumulation in the brain cells of fish. Lipofuscin was observed in heart of mature *Channa punctatus* [1].

Characteristics of Lipofuscin Pigments In Brain Cells of Mature Age Group

Age Group	Tissues	Morphological characteristics of lipofuscin pigments	Distribution of lipofuscin pigment
Mature	Brain	Heterogeneous and irregular	Irregularly scattered throughout the cytoplasm

Histochemical Nature Of Lipofuscin Pigment In Brain

Age group	Tissues	Nile blue A	Ferric ferricyanide	Carbol fuchsin
Mature	Brain	+++	++	+

Conclusion This observation is an agreement with the finding in the cells of Rana and Matrix reacted strongly with Nile blue A and moderately positive to ferric ferricyanide similarly these observations were used in [5]and [6].The present study are in agreement with those of [5], in neurons of young animals [6] observation in mature age the lipofuscin in nervous system, 5 months in dog. Similarly these stains were used in [5].

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